
The new political stage of the Middle East: Iran and its unyielding policies

Hasib Bin Shaharia * ^{1 A}; S.M.Shawlin ^{2 A}

*Corresponding author: ¹ e-mail: shahariar.bin@gmail.com

² e-mail: smshawlin888@gmail.com

^A Bangladesh University of Professionals, Mirpur Cantonment, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Received: November 20, 2022 | **Revised:** March 20, 2023 | **Accepted:** March 31, 2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7855498

Abstract

This study analytically investigates the Iranian policies and their various effect on the Middle East as well as how Iran become a dominating power in the new political stage of the Middle East. The study has also portrayed the historical, religious, and political differences which are the backbone of the present crisis. Mostly, the research is crafted in a way where analysis is made from numerous perspectives and shows how is it relevant on the basis of knowing the situation in depth. Politics is the key idea here but in the tree of politics, the research represents multifarious roots. Each of the roots is connected to the main topic. Additionally, roots are the light to see the whole picture. Research is also showing how policies are important and how Iran's unyielding position in terms of making policy is helping Iran to dominate the region. As it is a huge study area, more research is needed to understand every particle of that.

Key words: policy, politics, Middle East, Iran, unyielding.

Introduction

Persian history showcased their uncompromising action towards regional politics. It connects their interests on logical methods over the time as well as Islamic revolution and Arab Spring rebuild a new atmosphere to grapes the chance over again. In the new changing scenario of middle-east, Iran focuses on dominance over the region; precisely in socio-political area additionally achieving nuclear power to make a balance against Israel. Iran's policies on the most oil shipping route called Strait of Hormuz to set its militia throughout the region have introduced a huge political problem which opens end number of doors for the changed political sequences. Furthermore, the keen eyes show Iran's attitude are highly confronting on such issues like religion, politics, security, socio-culture and regional integration. The policies which Iran take have unyielding attitude likewise growing drone industry or nuclear deal with United State and its p5+1 partners. And all of those somehow arrange a new political stage in middle east. As a consequence, the players who are opposite to Iran initiated such diversifying plans such as creating I2U2 and GCC. Additionally, the sanction from USA and European Union has another initiative that helps others middle-east countries to set a balance with Iranian policies which is politically against to those countries. Moreover, Iran is playing for its own interest, and their political and regional and military advantages allow them to do whatever they want. This create a huge structural change into the region as middle east is already intimidated with chaotic conflicts. As far as the situation is, Iran's geographical benefits illustrate a picture where a hand full of color is in Iran's control. Apart from political point of view, world energy supply chain could be down, the fire of Eurasia can get more fuel or Russian dominance over the land all could happen due to Iran's policy which is now hard to break for imbalance regional security set-up.

Material and methods

According to, Atallah S. Al Sarhan in his article tries to show the foreign policy of Iran towards Iraq and the research gap is found that he only shows his view towards Iraq but not only other regions of Iran dominance over the other countries and in our paper we will try to show the actual dominance and the unyielding policies of Iran. In his paper Atallah only shows the economic dimension of a certain period of Iran's foreign policy that does not show any actual foreign policy of Iran.

According to, Fakhreddin Soltani and Reza Ekhtiari Amiri, in their paper they try to show the Iran foreign policy after the Islamic revolution in Iran and they try to show the perspective of Iran's foreign policy according to some president's regime and the research gap is found that they only show some particular regions and their way how Iran behaves on that region and that does not show a holistic view of Iran's foreign policy and in our paper we will try to show a holistic view of Iran's unyielding foreign policy.

According to, Ali Akbar Dareini in his article he tries to show the Iran's foreign policy under Ibrahim Raisi and in his paper he only shows a regime of only one person and the previous presidents foreign policy is ignored and in his paper he shows the economic resistance that Iran has over the rule of Raisi and he only compared the Asian economic circle not only other nations and that shows the research gap in the paper and we will try to show the actual unyielding foreign policies of Iran that shows a holistic view.

From the above perspective the research gap is clear and, in our paper, this could be the most significant issues of Iran's unyielding foreign policy.

Results

The Politics behind war in Middle East and Iranian Weapons

War has enormous impact on the picture of middle-east soil. Natural resources like oil, gas, gold and etc relief a great value to the region. Global politics, regional interest, and luxurious demands made the terror situations in true sense. Behind the real picture power politics of world powers, terrorist groups and undefined territory like Palestine are the key scenario for the horror situation. Iran has its implemented policies over the region enlisted to impact of those raising regional tension. Unstable setting in politics tells how inquisitive the overall arrangement is. In Syria, Lebanon, Jordan and Iraq war has limit all the normal life standard of common people. However, the contextual setup of middle-east countries has fallen down. The security is in risk for every country. Since Arab spring, a number of political crisis happen and that leads to war. The incentive picture got totally changed moreover war has begun. Unstable middle-east create immense opportunity to Iran as Iran took powerful control over the region. In Yemen, Houthi is supported by pro Iran force where in Lebanon Iran supports Hezbollah to control over the Lebanon. Those political benefits create huge impact on how unyielding policy Iran took over in any situation that Iran can still have.

In the upcoming year, Iran has developed its defense system and they try to develop some military weapons that will create impact on the war. Tehran has taken a project after the Iran-Iraq war to encounter the embargo that western has hit upon them. They have manufactured their own tanks, missiles, radars system, gun boats, submarines etc. They have developed their own aviation industry, most of them known as Shafaq, Qaher, Dorna etc. they have developed the heavy radar systems, known as BSR-1-VHF radar, Thamen-radar system. They have developed many short range missiles, mid-range missiles, anti-tank missiles, cruise missiles etc. They have also developed many naval missiles, torpedo, armored vehicles.

Discussion

1.1 Iran and its militants: the new changeable situation is in Iran's control

Iran supported militant groups are everywhere in the middle east. They are doing proxy war in their geographical boundaries but they are always ordered by Iranian IRGC (Islamic Revolutionary Guards Corps) which is both supportive and funding to them. By using them in particular territory, Iran has always putting pressure on selected countries like Israel, Saudi-Arabia, UAE etc.

Picture 1 – Iran's financial funding to the Militants

The system of controlling regional geopolitics has rely on comprehensive methods which differ in terms of what is workable what is not for specific countries. Methodically, countries like USA, China, Britain; they built military base to secure a position on specified field or region. Additionally, powerful countries support different militants group throughout the globe to create pressure on present governments or they just want ensure that their power should go away if those group ever take control over the government. Iran is similarly both supporting and funding militants to control political situation over middle-east. The chart illustrates Iran funds approximately 3000 million to different groups in Syria to keep Iranian interest always. Furthermore, Iran wants to secure a position where it could able to become threat to Israel and Turkey. Hezbollah gets total 700 million dollars by Iran to build strong position over in Lebanon to control and become potential threat to Israel and make influence in Lebanon's politics. Iran funds to both Hamas and Hauthis about 100 million. Iran's main opponent in middle east is Saudi Arabia. Taking into consideration, Iran helps Hauthis to give reasonable pressure on that. Even in Yemen's political conflict somehow arise Saudi's secure concern as well as Hauthis is making Iran position high in terms of consulting with countries like Saudi Arabia, UAE. Hamas is strong political power in Palestine and Iran is using them by forcing Israel for their own importance as well as for the rights of Palestine people.

1.2 Iran uses “Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action” as a tool to negotiate

In the field of politics every chance is variable. Even though opponent's chance could be beneficial if you can control the overall steps. “Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action” (JCPOA) or Iran's nuclear deal was signed in 2015 between Iran and P5+1(USA, UK, France, China, Russia+ Germany) to control on uranium production. Over the time the deal gets different complexity and Iran got sanction that primarily worsen the economy of Iran. In the same time, Iran is empowered in different sectors especially military equipment building. Now-a-days Iran drone technology is

performing utmost level in the region. Recently, Russia come to Iran and buy Iranian drones. That a gigantic move for Iran. Notwithstanding the sanction on Iran, P5+1 couldn't control Iran nuclear project even though international media says Iran is very close in term of becoming nuclear power. Although P5+1 puts a pressure by sanction on Iran, Iranian policies handle the overall situation and take some bold initiative to arise tension in other middle east countries. Iran's progress in building military equipments is becoming huge threat to its neighbors. So, even in the perplex situations, Iran has taken some extraordinary policies which make Iran more competitive in the region as well as Iran is in better position in negotiation with USA. Because by the years Iranian become more empower and self-defended which change the overall field in regional politics.

1.3 The impact of Eurasian politics in Middle East: How Iran's bilateral relation with both Russia and Turkey effect the region

The most influencing power of Eurasia have always political agenda in Middle East. Turkey has shared geographical boundaries with this region so political instability in Middle East create security threat to Turkey such as a large number of refugee is in turkey's territory, terrorist groups like PKK, YPG are making terrorist attack on Turkey and so on. For the consequence, Turkey puts military forces into Middle East region which portrayed change scenario in the territory. Beyond that, Russian emergence in the region and supportive to some specified groups that effect the whole socio-political atmosphere in there. Eventually, Iran has cooperative relation with Russia and Turkey whereas both of them are working as individual but keep Iran's interest in mind. American sanctions on Turkey, Russia and Iran; force them to become closer in political, economic and security purpose. So, middle east countries couldn't get direct support from regional super power Turkey and Russia against Iran. This political diplomacy that Iran practices add value on the Iran's credibility. Recently, Recep Tayyip Erdogan said that Turkey and Iran will take a military bilateral project to develop combat drone whereas Iran has numerous military cooperation with Russia too. So, Eurasian influence on the territory is in Iran side and they are using it perfectly. On the other hand, Israel's power in middle east is affluence but Israel couldn't be trustworthy to Eurasian countries due to its closeness with USA and its policy against Muslim community.

1.4 Religion (Shia vs Sunni)

In Iran most of the people considered as Muslim community. Iran's religion comparison is given down below:

Picture 2 – Iran's religion comparison

From the above chart we can say that in Iran 94% are Shia Muslim community and 5% is Sunni community and 1% or rest of the religion contains Baha'i, Christian and others.

In Iraq 65-70% of Muslim community are Shia and the rest 30-35% are Sunni community. In Lebanon the population is equal to its Sunni and Shia community. 45-55% of population in Lebanon is Shia and 45-55% of the Muslim community is Sunni. In Syria about 74% of the population is Sunni and only 1% population is Shia community. Shia community has the major difference in competence of Sunni community. In most of the region Shia and Sunni has the difference in their rituals in most cases Saudi Arabia has the Sunni community and Iran has the largest Shia community. Both Shia and Sunni has the impact on middle east politics. Today about eighty-five percent of the Muslims around 1.6 billion of them are Sunni and 15 percent of them are Shia. And most of the Shia community are living in Iran and they choose a supreme leader to lead their country. On the other hand, Saudi Arabia choose their king to lead the country as a supreme leader. Most of the cases middle east politics are centralized by these two countries.

1.4 Reaction of Arab against Iran`s policy

There is a major type of tie with relations of Arabs country against Iran, Oman and Qatar makes a major distance from Saudi Arabia and maintain close contact with Iran and on the other hand Egypt, Jordan, Kuwait and Bahrain which maintains the relation with Saudi Arabia and keeps distance with Iran. Any circumstance mainly in the political arena depends on the Saudi and Iran`s relation on their interest. Basically, their relations continue on three pivotal issues, and they are mainly Iran`s interest and their involvement on the issue of Yemen, Iran`s investment on the development of the life of Saudi Shias community, and another important issue is Saudis result of Nuclear weapons negotiations with United States of America. Iran`s foreign policy and the relation with the Arab world mainly fragile and not constant in the circumstance of the Iran`s opposition Israel and USA. And Saudi keep the close tie with the opposition of Iran`s relation. Now the global situation of Iran`s policy is in a tragic fuss with the uncertain death of MahsaAmini`s tragic death while in detention. A new quad has formed to maintain the cooperation of other bilateral relations and the name of this group is I2U2. This group has four member countries to strengthen their relations on many sector, India, Israel, UAE and USA. By this group Iran has the concern of their military cooperation that raise the tension between the relations of Saudi and Iran.

Conclusions

Policies have impactful importance in modern days. Now-a-days it brakes national boundary and come forward to international interest. After Islamic revolution, Iran`s relation among middle east countries have declining. Power politics, religion and Israel`s invasion in middle east raised a tension in the region which later create no compromising field for Iran and other middle east countries to build their relation once again. so. Iran has taking such decision which are in favor of Iran`s politics but raise tension for other countries. And that's how a new political stage has created. This particular research has shown some key factors behind that. And every background topic has its own way to rediscover the whole situation. In a short, Iran`s policies about increasing military strength, helping and creation militias, hostile relation with Saudi Arabia and Israel and try to imposing philosophy of Shia religion to others have tremendous effect on middle east politics. In response countries like UAE has created bilateral relation with Israel, Muslim countries can't unite in the crisis of Palestine, OIC can't make independent decisions. So, Iran`s unyielding policies have changed the over-all political situation of middle east.

References

- Amiri, Ekhtiari. Reza & Soltani Fakhreddin, Foreign Policy of Iran after Islamic revolution (2010, January).
- Arms control Organization, Iran, P5+1 Sign Nuclear (2013, Dec 12). Available from :

<https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2013-12/iran-p51-sign-nuclear-agreement>.

Dareini, Akbar. Ali, Iran's Foreign Policy under Raisi (2021, June 30). Available from :

<https://studies.aljazeera.net/en/analyses/iran%E2%80%99s-foreign-policy-under-raisi>

Pew research center, Many Sunnis and Shias worry about religious conflict, (2022, Nov 7). Available

from : <https://www.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/7/2013/11/Shias-Sunnis-religious-conflict-full-report>.

Pruitt, Sarah, Islam's Sunni-Shia Divide, Explained, the split between the two main sects within Islam goes back some 1,400 years (2022, Jan 10). Available from :

<https://www.history.com/news/sunni-shia-divide-islam-muslim>

Sarhan, Al S. Atallah, Economic Dimension in Iran's Foreign Policy Towards (2021, Oct 26), Iraq: 20032020, Available from :

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/07393148.2022.2060016>

Sariolghalam, Mahmood, Iran's playbook in the Arab world: Ideology or domestic politics? (2022, Oct 24). Available from : <https://www.mei.edu/publications/irans-playbook-arab-world-ideology-or-domestic-politics>.